

THE SOCIAL ACTIVITY OF WOMEN IS ONE OF THE IMPORTANT FACTORS IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF THE COUNTRY

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ABSTRACT

The article emphasizes the scientific orientation of increasing the social activity of women in Uzbekistan at the level of state policy and strategy. Also, socialization is a controlled and purposeful process of self-transformation and development throughout a person's life, socialization of women is a social environment that surrounds women, family, state and society, the media, education and science, work and activity. has been scientifically analyzed for widespread use in sports and culture, art and literature. In particular, activation is a distinctive feature, a dynamic activity, which means the ability to independently organize your time. The activity is characterized by purposefulness, motivation, initiative. Activity is also the ability to satisfy the needs of your soul, to be fully interested in life.

1. Introduction:

It is well known that socialization is a controlled and purposeful process of self-transformation and development throughout a person's life.

Socialization of women - we can include the social environment that surrounds women, family, state and society, media, education and science, work and activity, sports and culture, art and literature.

Activation is a unique feature, a dynamic activity that means being able to organize your time yourself. The activity is characterized by purposefulness, motivation, initiative. Activity is also the ability to satisfy the needs of your soul, to be fully interested in life.

Activating women is an opportunity to showcase women's desires and talents. Active women are often successful and show themselves in different areas of life.

A lot of work is being done in the country to ensure the rights and interests of women, create decent working and living conditions for them, realize their abilities and potential, build a strong civil society, ensure the rule of law, protect rights, freedoms and human rights. legitimate interests.

State Convention on the Rights of the Child, International Labor Organization Convention on Equal Incentives for Men and Women for Equal Work, Convention No. 103 on Maternity Protection and Discrimination in the Field of Work and Education.

Ratification of the Convention on the Elimination of All Forms of Discrimination against Women, the Convention on Employment Policy, the Convention on the Elimination of All Forms of Child Labor and the Convention on the Elimination of All Forms of Child Labor. Served as the necessary international legal basis for the development of specific measures in the legislation and practice of public authorities on the implementation of standards.

Within the framework of the adopted legislation, the Government, ministries and departments of Uzbekistan, non-governmental organizations systematically and consistently work to support and protect the rights of women and ensure their full participation in the socio-political, economic and cultural life of the country. ... As President Shavkat Mirziyoyev said: "We all understand that passing laws is only part of the job. The main task is to timely convey the essence of the laws to our people and responsible executors, to organize their implementation correctly and ensure strict observance of the law. Unfortunately, work in this direction is not in demand. In general, strengthening the organizational and legal mechanisms for ensuring women's rights in Uzbekistan and procedures for their implementation, consolidating the efforts of state structures and civil society institutions in this area, improving the legal culture of the population on women's rights. The role of political parties in the life of the country is determined by a clear vision of their political status, practical activities in accordance with their position, goals and objectives in the socio-political life of society. It is important that the increase in the socio-political status of women is precisely due to the activities of political parties.

2. Methods:

The article provides a scientific analysis of the state policy in the field of guardianship to ensure the rights and

interests of women, to increase their social activity.

3. Research results:

Further strengthening of the role of women in building the state and society, strengthening their political rights, support and cardinal improvement of family activities are also reflected in the "Action Strategy for the Five Priorities of the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2017-2021". "Therefore, the section of the Action Strategy" Tasks for further reforming the priorities of the social sphere "determines the improvement of social protection and health care, increasing the socio-political activity of women. It is also necessary to increase the socio-political activity of women, strengthen their role in the state and society, ensure the employment of women professional colleges, attract them to entrepreneurship, further strengthen the family base.

Today, through the rapid development of Uzbekistan, following the traditions of the wisdom of our ancestors, strict reforms are being carried out, a way is being paved to the formation of a new image of the country. In the works of our great ancestors Abu Nasr Farobi, Amir Temur, Alisher Navoi, Zakhiriddin Muhammad Babur, Abdullah Avloni, Abdurauf Fitrat, special attention is paid to the issue of the status of women. In particular, Alisher Navoi, in his works dedicated to the glorification of women and strengthening their status, emphasizes that "there are many women in the world who are famous for their intelligence, courage and wisdom, beauty, thoughtfulness and patience, and kindness. and loyalty." It is noteworthy that in recent years, in the course of new reforms in the country, priority attention is paid to mechanisms for the development of the social status of women, in particular, norms of international importance.

Since the goal of the renewed development of Uzbekistan is to achieve the Third Renaissance, one of the main tasks in this direction is to make women more

educated and enlightened. It should be noted that an enlightened woman is the path of development of society, because it is she who, raising her children to be knowledgeable, enlightened, highly spiritual, forms their consciousness, worldview, and level of knowledge. In society, the upbringing of a boy is seen as the upbringing of a person, and the upbringing of a girl is seen as the upbringing of a society, a nation. Because a woman, by her nature and creation, is entrusted with a great task - to continue the succession of generations and bring up children who will defend the dignity of the nation. However, the more educated and talented a girl becomes, the more she will pass this on to her children and the more responsibly she will approach the upbringing of a harmoniously developed generation.

According to Mariana Kemp, an American scientist who has studied the life and development of Uzbek women from ancient times to the present day, "in order to improve the lives of women, it is necessary to provide them with an excellent education and an environment for them to live. free activity. So that they can start their own small business, own their own income, and speak for their children and family. It is these factors that enhance the role of women in society.

In order to increase the social activity of women over the years of independence, public associations "Women-Lawyers", "Science and Women", "Creative Women", "Women-Entrepreneurs", "Women and Health", "Honorary Women" have been established. ... It has become a tradition to hold contests "Woman of the Year", "Exemplary Family".

In order to provide comprehensive support in the implementation of innovative ideas, projects and developments of women in the country, to increase the efficiency of projects implemented by women working in various fields of science, education and economy, the republic took part in the republican

competition "100 best innovative projects. Many women scientists, researchers, talented students and schoolgirls participated in new projects to present their technical projects, rationalization proposals, innovative developments in the sectors of the economy.

President of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev, noting the importance of the human factor for the current stage of development of our people, the fate and future of our country, said: "We all know that Uzbekistan has rich mineral and natural resources, strong economic and human resources. potential. However, our greatest asset is the enormous intellectual and spiritual potential of our people. "

In the final stage of the I Republican competition "100 best innovative projects of women of Uzbekistan", which was held on February 6-7, 2018 in the nomination "The most effective innovative project (in all priority areas of science and technology)" Academy of Sciences of the Republic of Uzbekistan UA S. Iskhakova, in Economics, Senior Researcher at the Institute of Ion-Plasma and Laser Technologies named after Arifova, took 1st place and was awarded the appropriate Diploma and memorable gifts. The nomination was attended by Ubaydullaeva and F. Bobodjonova "Best invention" on the topic "Creation of new varieties of cotton using gene knockout technology" and took first place. F. Bobojonova won in the republican stage of the competition in the nomination "The most effective innovative project" on the topic "The introduction of innovative technologies in the creation of new promising lines of potatoes."

4. Conclusions:

In short, the interests of women in Uzbekistan and the measures taken to increase their social activity are an expression of the state policy of care aimed at ensuring the rights and interests of women. As President Sh. Mirziyoyev said: "Attention to women should always be at

the center of all our efforts, this should be our common duty."

References:

1. Decree PF-4947-conli "On the Strategy of further development of the Republic of Uzbekistan" dated February 7, 2017, PF-February 2, 2018 "On measures to radically improve the activities in the field of support of women and strengthening the institution of the family" Decree No. 5325, Presidential Decree PQ-4235 of March 7, 2019 "On measures to further strengthen the guarantees of women's labor rights and support entrepreneurship", Decree of September 2, 2019 "On measures to further strengthen the guarantees of women's labor rights and support entrepreneurship" Law No. ZRU 561 "On protection from violence" and ZRU 562 "On guarantees of equal rights and opportunities for women and men" // lex.uz
2. Festive congratulations of President Sh. Mirziyoyev to the women of Uzbekistan // People's speech, March 7, 2018.
3. Djuraeva, N. Study of issues of relationship of the soviet state to women in western historiography. International Journal of Advanced Science and Technology, 2020, 29(5), стр. 1387–1391.
4. Djuraeva, N., Babadjanova, N., Bazarova, M. Supporting women, protecting their rights and interests is a priority in the state policy of Uzbekistan. International Journal of Advanced Science and Technology, 2020, 29(5), стр. 1392–1397
5. Khidirova B. The strategy for achieving gender equality is based on national and universal values // <https://yuz.uz/news/gender-equality-strategy-is-national-and-human-dignities>